

seedlings were planted per. hill. No insecticide was applied. All plants were scored for symptoms at 20 and 35 DT. Virus infection was indexed by ELISA from leaves taken from each hill in a sample of 5 × 5 hills. Ten samples were taken in W-pattern from each plot.

More *Nephotettix virescens* than *N. nigropictus* were collected within the nursery, but numbers were similar in the surrounding plants. Fewer infective GLH were found in the nursery (Table 1).

At 20 DT, RTV incidence was lower in plants in the screenhouse than in the field. At 35 DT, only a slight increase in incidence was observed in the screenhouse; in the field, incidence was nearly 100% (Table 2). This also indicates the low increase in number of GLH in the screenhouse, although it is suitable for GLH development.

Even under high disease and vector pressures, the unprotected wetbed seedling nursery had low RTV incidence. This may be due to the loss of

Table 1. GLH and infective vectors collected from a TN1-seeded nursery in the center of a RTV-affected field and from plants surrounding the nursery. IIRRI, 1989.

Collection site	GLH/10 sweeps ^a (no.)		Infective GLH ^b (%)		
	<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
In the nursery	45	9	0	3	1
Around the nursery	25	22	3	10	0

^a21 DAS. ^bNo infective *N. nigropictus* was obtained. Infectivity of 80 GLH/site was tested using 1 GLH/TN1 seedling for 24-h inoculation in test tube at 21 DAS. RTBV = rice tungro bacilliform virus, RTSV = rice tungro spherical virus. Plants were assayed by ELISA 21 d after inoculation.

Table 2. RTV incidence based on symptoms and infection by RTBV and RTSV of TN1 plants^a at 20 and 35 d after transplanting (DT) in the screenhouse and in the field. IIRRI, 1989.

	RTV incidence (%)							
	20 DT			35 DT				
	Visual score	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	Visual score	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
Screenhouse	1	2	3	1	7	7	5	4
Field	27	24	7	14	99	91	4	3

^aFrom a 2- × 10-m nursery at the center of a RTV-infected field. Plants were indexed by ELISA.

vector infectivity after feeding on seedlings in succession and to the low probability of the vector recovering its

infectivity by feeding on diseased seedlings. □

Effect of foliar application of various salts on rice sheath rot (ShR) disease

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We studied the effectiveness of different salts in controlling ShR incidence in rice crop in the greenhouse and in the field.

In the greenhouse experiment, two seeds of susceptible cultivar ADT38 were planted/clay pot, 5 pots/treatment, with five replications. At 90 d after seeding, eight salts at three concentrations were spray applied.

The plants were artificially inoculated with ShR pathogen *Acrocylin-drium oryzae* Sawada 24 h after spraying by inserting a diseased grain into the leaf sheath. ShR incidence was recorded 15 d after inoculation.

Sprays of calcium sulfate and magnesium sulfate up to 0.2% con-

centration reduced ShR incidence (Table 1).

The field experiment Sep-Feb 1989 (when disease incidence was high) was laid out in 4.5- × 2.0-m plots in a complete random block design with four replications. Susceptible cultivar Co 43 was transplanted 11 Sep, 30 d after seeding.

Recommended 150-60-30 kg NPK/ha was applied as urea, super-phosphate, and muriate of potash. P

Table 1. Effect of various salts on rice ShR incidence in the greenhouse.

Salt	Disease intensity ^a at given concentration		
	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%
Calcium sulfate	1.3	1.5	1.0
Magnesium sulfate	1.3	1.5	2.4
Copper sulfate	5.7	5.6	7.5
Ferrous sulfate	4.0	5.0	2.3
Zinc sulfate	5.0	2.8	1.9
Nickel nitrate	4.7	5.0	1.9
Sodium fluoride	4.0	1.0	1.2
Ammonium molybdate ^b	1.4	2.5	2.0
Untreated check	-	-	6.0

^aStandard evaluation system for rice, 0-9 scale. ^bTested at 10, 50, and 100 ppm.

and K were basal; N was applied in three equal splits at planting, tillering, and panicle initiation.

Nine salts were mixed in water and sprayed at the boot leaf stage and 15 d later (the check was sprayed with plain water). ShR incidence was measured as percentage tillers affected on randomly selected 25 hills/plot.

Manganese sulfate, calcium sulfate, ferrous sulfate, and copper sulfate gave ShR incidence significantly lower than that of the check (Table 2). □

Table 2. Effect of various salts on rice ShR incidence in the field. Aduthurai, India, Sep-Feb 1989.

Treatment	Concentration	Mean ShR (%)
Zinc sulfate	10 ⁻² M	22.3
Manganese sulfate	10 ⁻² M	14.0
Copper sulfate	10 ⁻² M	19.0
Calcium sulfate	10 ⁻² M	16.7
Ferric chloride	10 ⁻² M	25.6
Magnesium sulfate	10 ⁻² M	22.2
Ferrous sulfate	10 ⁻² M	18.2
Sodium borate	10 ⁻² M	20.1
Ammonium molybdate	10 ⁻³ M	24.3
Untreated check		31.2
LSD (P=0.05)		6.6